

TABLE I—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BERYLLIUM, MAGNESIUM AND CALCIUM WITH BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID AS INDICATOR

Amount of alkali metal taken mg	Beryllium			Magnesium			Calcium		
	Found mg	Error	SD	Found mg	Error	SD	Found mg	Error	SD
0.25	0.28	+0.02	±0.08	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.50	0.50	+0.00	±0.01	0.50	0.00	±0.01	0.47	+0.08	±0.04
0.75	0.76	-0.01	±0.02	—	—	—	0.77	-0.02	±0.03
1.00	0.98	+0.02	±0.02	—	—	—	0.98	+0.02	±0.02
1.20	—	—	—	1.20	0.00	±0.01	—	—	—
2.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.01	-0.01	±0.01
2.25	—	—	—	2.24	-0.01	±0.02	2.25	0.00	±0.01
2.50	2.52	-0.02	±0.02	—	—	—	—	—	—
3.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.98	+0.02	±0.02
3.36	—	—	—	3.35	+0.01	±0.02	—	—	—
4.00	—	—	—	3.98	+0.02	±0.03	4.02	-0.02	±0.03
4.50	—	—	—	4.51	-0.01	±0.02	—	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.00	±0.02	—	—	—	5.01	-0.01	±0.02
Effective concentration range (mg)	0.10-20			0.10-25			0.10-25		

colour change is yellow to red. The results are shown in Table I.

Magnesium could not be determined quantitatively beyond this pH range.

Effect of diverse ions: Magnesium could be easily titrated in presence of Be^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} at pH 9-10. In presence of tartrate and tartaric acid magnesium could be titrated from Cd^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , Ni^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Al^{3+} .

Calcium interferes in the determination of magnesium and this can be masked with oxalic acid. 2.5-3.0 times the theoretically calculated amount of oxalic acid is required to mask calcium.

Calcium:

Calcium (0.1-0.5 mg) is mixed with standard EDTA solution, the pH is adjusted to 9-10 with ammonium hydroxide (0.1 M) and ammonium chloride (0.1 M) and titrated with standard iron(III) solution using benzohydroxamic acid as indicator. The colour change is yellow to red. The results are shown in Table I.

Calcium could not be determined quantitatively beyond this range.

Effect of the diverse ions: Results are the same as those for magnesium.

Magnesium interferes in the determination of calcium which can be masked with double the amount of iron(III).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.D.R.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

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N-Hydroxy-N-p-Chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-Dimethylphenyl-p-toluidine Hydrochloride—a New Reagent for the Gravimetric Determination of Molybdenum(VI)

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Manuscript received 30 July 1981, revised 30 September 1983, accepted 27 February 1984

VARIOUS reagents have been recommended for gravimetric determination of molybdenum. Of routine use are α -benzoinoxime¹, 8-hydroxyquinoline² and N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine³. In most of these methods lack of selectivity is often a serious disadvantage. The present paper describes a simple and highly selective method for gravimetric determination of molybdenum and its separation from diverse ions. Though the method does not afford a directly weighable precipitate, yet it can advantageously be applied to selectively estimate molybdenum in pH range 3.0-7.0.

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Experimental

A standard solution of molybdenum(VI) was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate, A.R. in glass distilled water. The amount of molybdenum in this solution was determined using 8-hydroxyquinoline².

A systronic pH meter, type 322 was used for pH measurements. The precipitated complex was collected on Whatman filter paper (No. 42, 11 cm) and ignited in silica crucible.

The reagent, N-hydroxy-N-*p*-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamidine hydrochloride, was prepared by the condensation of N-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluimidoyl chloride with equimolar N-*p*-chlorophenyl hydroxylamine in ether medium. A 3% (w/v) alcoholic solution of the reagent was used for precipitation purposes. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Recommended procedure: An aliquot of the test solution, containing 4-40 mg of the metal is diluted to 200 ml in a 400 ml beaker. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 4.5-6.5 using acetic acid and dilute ammonia. The solution is warmed to 60-70° and 3% alcoholic solution of the reagent (20 ml per 30 mg molybdenum) is added slowly with constant stirring. The instantaneously precipitated orange-yellow complex is digested on water bath for 15-20 min with occasional stirring and then filtered through a Whatman filter paper. The complex is washed several times with warm water and dried at 105° for 20-25 min. It is then transferred along with the filter paper to a silica crucible and carefully ignited at 500-550° till MoO₃ acquires a bright appearance with no trace of black particles. The amount of the metal is calculated from the weight of MoO₃, using the conversion factor of 0.66654.

Optimum experimental conditions: The precipitation of molybdenum complex commences at pH 0.8 and is quantitative in the pH range 3.0-7.0. However, the most suitable pH range for the determination of molybdenum is 4.5-6.5, in which a granular and easily filtrable precipitate is obtained.

At least 2.0-2.5 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent is necessary for complete precipitation. An excess of reagent (0.7 g) in a final volume of 200 ml have no interfering effect on the determination. In practice, for each mg of molybdenum, 20 mg of the reagent was employed.

Properties and composition of the complex: The dioxomolybdenum complex was orange-yellow in colour and soluble in common organic solvents such as alcohol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated by combustion method. (Found: Mo, 11.12; C, 61.69; H, 4.65; N, 6.47. Calcd. for MoO₂(C₂₂H₂₀N₂OCl)₂; Mo, 11.21; C, 61.75; H, 4.67; N, 6.55%). The 1:2 stoichiometry is confirmed by conductometric and pH metric studies. The formula of the complex may therefore be represented as MoO₂(C₂₂H₂₀N₂OCl)₂.

Infrared spectra: The displacement of C=N (1610 cm⁻¹) and N-O (930 cm⁻¹) stretching frequencies to 1575 and 960 cm⁻¹, respectively along with the disappearance of the =N⁺-H frequency (2550 cm⁻¹) of the free ligand in the complex suggest the formation of M-O bond, deprotonation of the azomethine nitrogen atom (C-N⁺-H) and metal coordination through it by forming C=N. M type of bond. The presence of MoO₂ group has been confirmed from the ir spectrum of the complex. A strong band at 920 cm⁻¹ is truly indicative of a O=Mo=O species, as oxo-metal cation such as Mo=O, involving a single oxygen metal multiple covalent bond absorbs at considerably higher region around 970-980 cm⁻¹. Similar assignments of dioxomolybdenum group has been made to the presence of a strong band around 910-920 cm⁻¹ in the molybdenum complexes of several other ligands such as oxine, N-benzoylphenyl hydroxylamine and Schiff bases.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions on the gravimetric determination of molybdenum(VI) with the reagent has been studied. Chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, oxalate, citrate, borate, phosphate and alkali metals do not interfere upto 500 mg. The tolerance limits of other ions causing an error less than 2% are given in parenthesis (in mg) Co²⁺(90); Mn²⁺(100); Zn²⁺(120); Al³⁺(95); Hg²⁺(70); Bi³⁺(100); Th⁴⁺(160); Zr⁴⁺(80); Ti³⁺(160); La³⁺(160). The interference due to Cu²⁺(100); Ni²⁺(90); Cr³⁺(110); Fe³⁺(90) and V⁵⁺(25) could be avoided in presence of 2 g EDTA. Ti⁴⁺(30) could be masked with 5 ml H₂O₂ (20 vol) and 20 ml 10% EDTA. In presence of UO₂²⁺(130) the determination should be carried out at pH 3.2. The interference due to Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺(50) could be eliminated by using tartaric acid (1 g) and NH₄-HF₂(500 mg). However, the interference due to W⁶⁺ could not be overcome.

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A New Method for Extractive Photometric Determination of Copper and Iron in Alloy Steel

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Manuscript received 13 January 1982, revised 24 June 1983,
accepted 27 February 1984

QUINOLINE-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (QAT) has been used in this laboratory for extractive spectrophotometric determination of nickel and palladium¹. Extension of these studies revealed